

Adjustment and Challenges of Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers in K to 12 Curriculum

Paulo M. Orioste¹, Marc Sylvester P. Garcia^{2*}

¹College of Agriculture, Laguna State Polytechnic University, Philippines

² College of Agriculture, Laguna State Polytechnic University, Philippines

Abstract:- The study aims to determine the Adjustments and Challenges of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers in K to 12 Curriculum in Schools Division Office of Laguna.. Adjustment of teachers in teaching TLE in K to 12 Curriculum showed that they had huge adjustments in Teaching Strategies which was closed to assessment, followed by instructional materials while the least was school environment. The challenges of TLE teachers encountered came out that they had equal distributions on having difficulties in terms of Information Communication Technology (ICT) Integration, Industrial Arts and Agri-Fishery Arts unlike in Home Economics.

The respondents enhance their teaching strategies, assessment task and instructional materials. Likewise, TLE teachers were challenged in ICT, Industrial Arts and Agri-Fishery Arts due to insufficient equipment and resources, minimal collaboration with partner agencies that could provide needed required expertise. It is recommended that enhancement and strengthening of skills could be attained if teachers will be given equal chances to attend relevant trainings and seminars, Upliftment of teacher's qualification and performances will be attained if coordination with other partner agencies could be develop. Higher student's achievement will be gained if teachers could adopt on the changing needs of time.

Keywords:- Adjustment, Challenges, Technology And Livelihood Education, K To 12 Curriculum

I. INTRODUCTION

Technology and Livelihood Education teachers have experienced adjustments and challenges in the curriculum. A teacher, who starts from the Basic Education Curriculum (10 years), where the paper and pencil test is the best example of traditional teaching, mainly describes and measures student

learning outcomes. Then the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 or the K to 12 Curriculum, where advanced teaching method is adopted. Teachers make significant adjustments in doing lesson plans from weekly to daily and the most challenging on how they will approach and think appropriate methods for the students.

Based on the above scenario, the researcher was motivated to conduct a study on determining the adjustments and challenges of TLE Teachers in K to 12 Program in Northeastern Laguna with the end in view that the findings of this study may merit educational leaders, curriculum planners, teachers, students, and future researchers.

Thus, the researcher was greatly challenged to conduct a study on "Adjustments and Challenges of Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers in K to 12 Program in Northeastern Laguna" in the hope that its findings would overhaul and streamline among Secondary Teachers in Public High Schools in Northeastern, Laguna.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Research Design

Descriptive designs include a survey under the descriptive method, and correlation research is commonly employed. In correlation research, the aim is to describe the strength of the relationship between two or more events or characteristics. (Salmorin, 2005)

Quantitative methods emphasize the objective measurements and the statistical, mathematical, or numerical data collected through polls, questionnaires, and surveys, or by manipulating pre-existing statistical data using computational techniques. (Babbie, 2010)

This method was appropriate to determine the teaching adjustments and challenges of the TLE teachers in the K to 12 Curriculum.

B. Subject of the Study

The respondents of the study consisted of 56 Technology and Livelihood Education (Junior) teachers from Northeastern, Laguna public high schools, namely: Poton & Eliseo M. Quesada Memorial National High School, Famy Integrated National High School, Balian Integrated National High School, Mabitac Integrated National High School, Sta. Maria Integrated High School and Siniloan Integrated National High School.

C. Sampling Techniques

The researcher undertook this study in different public high schools in Northeastern, Laguna. Since the number of respondents was 56, the researcher used the total enumeration to make the study acceptable and essential.

Total enumeration sampling is a type of purposive sampling technique that involves examining the entire population that have a particular set of characteristics (e.g., specific attributes/traits, experience, knowledge, skills, exposure to an event, etc.) while total population sampling is infrequently used since there are specific types of research where total population sampling can be beneficial.

D. Research Instruments

The primary tool used in this study was a checklist questionnaire. The questionnaire is a set of printed or written that answers according to the professional background of the respondents devised for a survey or statistical study.

The data collected from this research helped the teachers to evaluate their strengths and weaknesses to improve their instruction.

Also, this research instrument allowed the researcher to carry out the quantitative approach effectively with the use of statistics for data interpretation.

➤ Paper Title

Adjustment and Challenges of Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers in K to 12 Curriculum

➤ Authorship

List the first and last names of all authors. Provide the full affiliation for each author including Department, University, City, Zip Code, State, Country. If any of the co-authors are from different organizations, their affiliation should be numbered with different Arabic numerals. Email address is compulsory for the corresponding author.

e.g. Paulo M. Orioste¹, Marc Sylvester P. Garcia

¹College of Agriculture, Laguna State Polytechnic University, 4016, Philippines

² College of Agriculture, Laguna State Polytechnic University, 4016, Philippines

III. 3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The plurality of the teacher-respondents was ranging from 31-40 years old, and they were in the middle –age of teaching. Fifty (50) out of fifty-six respondents were female, six (6) were male and most of them were married, and Master's degree - unit earners. Most of the distance of teacher-respondents residency from work was one kilometer. Half of the number of teacher-respondents in their field of specialization was Home Economics and mostly were handling 2-3 preparations with 5-6 hours of teaching per day.

Majority of the teacher-respondents were working in the service for about 0-5 years with an equal distribution in number of training/seminars attended for the past two years since K to 12 curricula was implemented in the country. Thirty (30) of them were Teacher 1 in Academic Rank/Designation in school where they were working.

Adjustments of teacher-respondents in teaching TLE in K to 12 Curriculum showed in Table 1 that they had huge adjustments in Teaching Strategies which was closed to Assessment, followed by Instructional Materials while the least was School Environment. It implies that the teachers should use instructional materials that are relevant and suitable for the level of learners and the activities that they are going to do fitted to their level.

Table 1. Adjustments of TLE Teachers in K to 12 curricula

ADJUSTMENTS	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
A. SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT ADJUSTMENTS		
1. Managing students' discipline in the class pose a problem.	3.41	Often
2. Laboratory rooms and facilities are insufficient for laboratory class.	3.07	Sometimes
3. The school guidelines and policies are hard to follow.	2.41	Seldom
4. The laboratory equipment of TLE is hard/ difficult to use'	2.36	Seldom
5. There are interpersonal conflicts and communication problems in TLE organizational management and relationship.	2.16	Seldom
<i>Average Weighted Mean</i>	2.68	Sometimes
B. TEACHING STRATEGIES ADJUSTMENTS		
1. Provide and be innovative in giving hands-on – activities in TLE curricula.	3.88	Often
2. TLE curriculum proposes varied strategies which are raw for teachers.	3.63	Often
3. I have to engage myself in hands on laboratory exercises of the students	4.11	Always
4. Choose and follow the prescribed indoor and outdoor activities.	4.00	Often
5. Provide clever and imaginative motivational activities to motivate students through engagement	4.07	Often
<i>Average Weighted Mean:</i>	3.94	Often
C. INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS ADJUSTMENTS		
1. Familiarization on the additional resources and materials for teaching TLE in K to 12 Curriculum.	4.11	Often
2. Requiring my students to bring different tools/materials/equipment available in their homes for lesson due to insufficiency of materials in school.	3.21	Sometimes
3. Providing the students downloaded educational programs, audio visual presentations, software PowerPoint to catch their attitudes and motivations.	3.88	Often
4. The ratio of books is not equated to the number of students.	3.43	Often
5. Instructional materials are difficult to facilitate and prepare.	3.02	Sometimes
<i>Average Weighted Mean</i>	3.53	Often
D. ASSESSMENT ADJUSTMENTS		
1. I consider/ use performance –based assessment besides traditional paper-and – pencil formative tests.	4.05	Often

2. Be more adaptive to the new assessment tools and methodologies of TLE curriculum.	3.93	Often
3. It is hard to determine the learning abilities and potentials of student due to multiple assessment and methodologies.	3.18	Sometimes
4. Provide multiple ways of measuring their varying abilities and learning potentials	3.77	Often
5. Inform the parents about their child's learning, and work with school to help plans and provide support	3.71	Often
<i>Average Weighted Mean</i>	3.73	Often

The challenges of TLE teachers encountered came out that they had equal distributions on having difficulties in terms of ICT Integration, Industrial Arts and Agri-Fishery Arts unlike in Home Economics.

There is a significant relationship between school environment and challenges in terms of Home Economics and Industrial Arts. There is also a relationship between teaching strategies and challenges in Agri-Fishery Arts while there is no significant relationship between instructional materials in any variables in challenges.

There is a significant relationship between the distance of residency to school in teaching strategies and assessment of TLE teachers in teaching while the other profile such as age, sex, civil status, and educational attainment, field of sub-specialization, number of preparations and number of teaching hours per day between adjustments has no significant relationship.

There is a significant relationship between the respondents' profile in age and ICT. Also, there is a relationship between the number of preparation and Agri-Fishery Arts while the other profile such as sex, civil status, educational attainment, the distance of residency to school, field of sub-specialization and the number of teaching hours per day and challenges have no relationship.

There is a significant relationship between the number of training/seminars attended for the last two years and teaching strategies as well as Instructional materials while there is no relationship between the length of services and academic rank/designation with their adjustments such as their school environment, teaching strategies, instructional materials and

Assessment.

Lastly, there is a significant relationship between the qualifications of teacher and Agri-Fishery Arts while others are not significant with their challenges.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that:

1. Teachers often enhance their teaching strategies, assessment tasks and Instructional Materials.
2. Technology and Livelihood Education teachers were challenged in Information Communication Technology, Industrial Arts, Agri-Fishery and Home Economics due to insufficient equipment and resources, minimal collaboration with partner agencies that could provide needed required expertise.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Teachers matter, but they do not work in a vacuum, experiencing a lot of adjustments and challenges in the world of teaching. Their ability to elevate students' understanding depends on the schools, districts, and communities where they work and the professional communities to which they belong. The recommendations below are intended to address the issues identified in the conclusions with particular attention to the ways that the current education system needs to be changed to support teachers' on-going learning as they respond to the demands placed by current reforms in K to 12 Curriculum. With the results of the data gathered, the following recommendations were drawn:

1. Enhancement and strengthening of skills could be attained if teachers will be given equal chances to attend relevant trainings and seminars.

2. Upliftment of teachers' qualifications and performances will be attained if coordination with other partner agencies could be developed.
3. Higher students' achievements will be gained if teachers could adopt on the changing needs of times.

Any comments and suggestions are welcomed so that we can constantly improve this template to satisfy all authors' research needs.

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